

Supplementary Material 1.PRISMA 2020 Main Checklist

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	4
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	5&6
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	5
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	5
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	5
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	6&7
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the	6

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
		methods used to decide which results to collect.	
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	-
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	7
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	6
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item 5)).	6
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	6&7
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	-
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	6
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	-
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	-
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	7
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	8
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the	8

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
		number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	8
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	9
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	10
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	10-13
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	10-13
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	10-13
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	-
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	-
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	10
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	10
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	13&14
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	14
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	15
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	14&15
OTHER INFORMATION			

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	5
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	5
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	5
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	17
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	16
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	16&17

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *MetaArXiv*. 2020, September 14. DOI: 10.31222/osf.io/v7gm2. For more information, visit: www.prisma-statement.org

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

The detailed search strategy for PubMed						
Search number	Query	Sort By	Filters	Search Details	Results	Time
7	(("Osteoarthritis"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((Osteoarthritis[Title/Abstract]) OR (Osteoarthritides[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthrosis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthroses[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthritis, Degenerative[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthritides, Degenerative[Title/Abstract])) OR (Degenerative Arthritides[Title/Abstract])) OR (Degenerative Arthritis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthrosis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthroses[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthrosis Deformans[Title/Abstract]))) AND (("Dietary Supplements"[Mesh]) OR (((((((((((((((Dietary Supplements[Title/Abstract]) OR (Dietary Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Dietary Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplementations, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food			(("Osteoarthritis"[MeSH Terms] OR ("Osteoarthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR "arthritis degenerative"[Title/Abstract] OR ("Arthritis"[MeSH Terms] OR "Arthritis"[All Fields] OR "Arthritides"[All Fields] OR "polyarthritides"[All Fields]) AND "Degenerative"[Title/Abstract]) OR "degenerative arthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "degenerative arthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR "osteoarthrosis deformans"[Title/Abstract])) AND ("Dietary Supplements"[MeSH Terms] OR ("Dietary	805	11:16:35

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

	<p>Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Neutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Herbal[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Herbal[Title/Abstract]))</p>			<p>Supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplementations dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement food"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements food"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Neutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement herbal"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements herbal"[Title/Abstract]))</p>		
6	("Dietary Supplements"[Mesh]) OR			"Dietary Supplements"[MeSH	121,392	11:13:43

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

<p>((((((((((((((((((Dietary Supplements[Title/Abstract]) OR (Dietary Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Dietary Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplementations, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Neutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Herbal[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Herbal[Title/Abstract]))</p>			<p>Terms] OR "Dietary Supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplementations dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement food"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements food"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Neutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Neutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement herbal"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements herbal"[Title/Abstract]</p>		
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Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

5	<p>((((((((((((((((((Dietary Supplements[Title/Abstract]) OR (Dietary Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Dietary Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplementations, Dietary[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplementations[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Food Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Food[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceuticals[Title/Abstract])) OR (Nutriceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Neutraceutical[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplements[Title/Abstract])) OR (Herbal Supplement[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplement, Herbal[Title/Abstract])) OR (Supplements, Herbal[Title/Abstract])</p>		<p>"dietary supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "dietary supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplementations dietary"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplementations"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "food supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement food"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements food"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceuticals"[Title/Abstract] OR "Nutriceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "Neutraceutical"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplements"[Title/Abstract] OR "herbal supplement"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplement herbal"[Title/Abstract] OR "supplements herbal"[Title/Abstract]</p>	33,264	11:13:19
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Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

4	"Dietary Supplements"[Mesh]	Most Recent		"Dietary Supplements"[MeSH Terms]	99,587	11:07:41	
3	("Osteoarthritis"[Mesh]) OR ((((((((((Osteoarthritis[Title/Abstract]) OR (Osteoarthritides[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthrosis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthroses[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthritis, Degenerative[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthritides, Degenerative[Title/Abstract])) OR (Degenerative Arthritides[Title/Abstract])) OR (Degenerative Arthritis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthrosis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Arthroses[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthrosis Deformans[Title/Abstract]))			"Osteoarthritis"[MeSH Terms] OR ("Osteoarthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR "arthritis degenerative"[Title/Abstract] OR ("Arthritis"[MeSH Terms] OR "Arthritis"[All Fields] OR "Arthritides"[All Fields] OR "polyarthritides"[All Fields]) AND "Degenerative"[Title/Abstract]) OR "degenerative arthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "degenerative arthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR "osteoarthrosis deformans"[Title/Abstract])	118,148	11:05:36	
2	(((((((((((Osteoarthritis[Title/Abstract]) OR (Osteoarthritides[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthrosis[Title/Abstract])) OR (Osteoarthroses[Title/Abstract])) OR				"Osteoarthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Osteoarthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR	98,279	11:04:28

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

	(Arthritis, Degenerative[Title/Abstract]) OR (Arthritides, Degenerative[Title/Abstract]) OR (Degenerative Arthritides[Title/Abstract]) OR (Degenerative Arthritis[Title/Abstract]) OR (Arthrosis[Title/Abstract]) OR (Arthroses[Title/Abstract]) OR (Osteoarthrosis Deformans[Title/Abstract])			"arthritis degenerative"[Title/Abstract] OR (("Arthritis"[MeSH Terms] OR "Arthritis"[All Fields] OR "Arthritides"[All Fields] OR "polyarthritides"[All Fields]) AND "Degenerative"[Title/Abstract]) OR "degenerative arthritides"[Title/Abstract] OR "degenerative arthritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthrosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arthroses"[Title/Abstract] OR "osteoarthrosis deformans"[Title/Abstract]		
1	"Osteoarthritis"[Mesh]	Most Recent		"Osteoarthritis"[MeSH Terms]	76,709	11:00:49

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

The detailed search strategy for Embase			
No.	Query	Results	Date
#36	#22 AND #35	860	27-May-23
#35	#23 OR #24 OR #25 OR #26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29 OR #30 OR #31 OR #32 OR #33 OR #34	188913	27-May-23
#34	'osteoarthritis deformans':ab,ti	155	27-May-23
#33	'arthroses':ab,ti	611	27-May-23
#32	'arthritis':ab,ti	7810	27-May-23
#31	'degenerative arthritis':ab,ti	1696	27-May-23
#30	'degenerative arthritides':ab,ti	15	27-May-23
#29	'arthritides, degenerative':ab,ti	0	27-May-23
#28	'arthritis, degenerative':ab,ti	76	27-May-23
#27	'osteoarthritis':ab,ti	4474	27-May-23
#26	'osteoarthritis':ab,ti	4474	27-May-23
#25	'osteoarthritides':ab,ti	4	27-May-23
#24	'osteoarthritis':ab,ti	117990	27-May-23
#23	'osteoarthritis'/exp	162001	27-May-23
#22	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21	54213	27-May-23
#21	'supplements, herbal':ab,ti	94	27-May-23
#20	'supplement, herbal':ab,ti	12	27-May-23
#19	'herbal supplement':ab,ti	716	27-May-23
#18	'herbal supplements':ab,ti	1429	27-May-23
#17	'nutraceutical':ab,ti	212	27-May-23
#16	'nutraceuticals':ab,ti	164	27-May-23
#15	'nutriceutical':ab,ti	125	27-May-23
#14	'nutriceuticals':ab,ti	148	27-May-23
#13	'nutraceutical':ab,ti	8325	27-May-23
#12	'nutraceuticals':ab,ti	5895	27-May-23
#11	'supplements, food':ab,ti	70	27-May-23
#10	'supplement, food':ab,ti	58	27-May-23

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

#9	'food supplement':ab,ti	2453	27-May-23
#8	'food supplements':ab,ti	3415	27-May-23
#7	'food supplementations':ab,ti	11	27-May-23
#6	'supplementations, dietary':ab,ti	3	27-May-23
#5	'dietary supplementations':ab,ti	132	27-May-23
#4	'supplements, dietary':ab,ti	140	27-May-23
#3	'dietary supplements':ab,ti	12652	27-May-23
#2	'dietary supplement':ab,ti	8649	27-May-23
#1	'dietary supplement'/exp	22396	27-May-23

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

The detailed search strategy for Web of Science					
Database permissions	#	Search strategy	Database	Search Results	Date
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WOS.IC: 1993 to 2023 - WOS.CCR: 1985 to 2023 - WOS.SCI: 1980 to 2023 - WOS.AHCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ESCI: 2018 to 2023 - WOS.ISTP: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.SSCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ISSHP: 2000 to 2023 	1	TS=(Dietary Supplements) OR TS=(Dietary Supplement) OR TS=(Supplements, Dietary) OR TS=(Dietary Supplementations) OR TS=(Supplementations, Dietary) OR TS=(Food Supplementations) OR TS=(Food Supplements) OR TS=(Food Supplement) OR TS=(Supplement, Food) OR TS=(Supplements, Food) OR TS=(Nutraceuticals) OR TS=(Nutraceutical) OR TS=(Nutriceuticals) OR TS=(Nutriceutical) OR TS=(Neutraceuticals) OR TS=(Neutraceutical) OR TS=(Herbal Supplements) OR TS=(Herbal Supplement) OR TS=(Supplement, Herbal) OR TS=(Supplements, Herbal)	Web of Science	103634	Sun May 28 2023 00:45:56 GMT+0800
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WOS.IC: 1993 to 2023 - WOS.CCR: 1985 to 2023 - WOS.SCI: 1980 to 2023 - WOS.AHCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ESCI: 2018 to 2023 	2	TS=(Osteoarthritis) OR TS=(Osteoarthritis) OR TS=(Osteoarthroses) OR TS=(Osteoarthrosis) OR TS=(Osteoarthroses) OR TS=(Arthritis, Degenerative) OR TS=(Arthritis, Degenerative) OR TS=(Degenerative Arthritis) OR TS=(Degenerative Arthritis) OR TS=(Arthrosis) OR TS=(Arthroses) OR TS=(Osteoarthrosis Deformans)	Web of Science	120749	Sun May 28 2023 00:45:57 GMT+0800

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WOS.ISTP: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.SSCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ISSHP: 2000 to 2023 					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WOS.IC: 1993 to 2023 - WOS.CCR: 1985 to 2023 - WOS.SCI: 1980 to 2023 - WOS.AHCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ESCI: 2018 to 2023 - WOS.ISTP: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.SSCI: 2000 to 2023 - WOS.ISSHP: 2000 to 2023 	3	#1 AND #2	Web of Science	729	Sun May 28 2023 00:45:57 GMT+0800

Supplementary Material 2.The detailed search strategy

The detailed search strategy for Cochrane Library

Date Run: 27/05/2023 18:36:43

Comment:

ID Search Hits

#1 MeSH descriptor: [Osteoarthritis] explode all trees 10385

#2 (Osteoarthritis):ti,ab,kw OR (Osteoarthritis):ti,ab,kw OR (Osteoarthrosis):ti,ab,kw OR (Osteoarthroses):ti,ab,kw OR (Arthritis, Degenerative):ti,ab,kw 22621

#3 (Arthritis, Degenerative):ti,ab,kw OR (Degenerative Arthritis):ti,ab,kw OR (Degenerative Arthritis):ti,ab,kw OR (Arthritis):ti,ab,kw AND (Arthroses):ti,ab,kw 345

#4 (Osteoarthrosis Deformans):ti,ab,kw 6

#5 #1 or #2 or #3 or #4 22623

#6 MeSH descriptor: [Dietary Supplements] explode all trees 16822

#7 (Dietary Supplement):ti,ab,kw OR (Dietary Supplements):ti,ab,kw OR (Supplements, Dietary):ti,ab,kw OR (Dietary Supplementations):ti,ab,kw OR (Supplementations, Dietary):ti,ab,kw 21075

#8 (Food Supplementations):ti,ab,kw OR (Food Supplements):ti,ab,kw OR (Food Supplement):ti,ab,kw OR (Supplement, Food):ti,ab,kw OR (Supplements, Food):ti,ab,kw 5636

#9 (Nutraceuticals):ti,ab,kw OR (Nutraceutical):ti,ab,kw OR (Nutriceuticals):ti,ab,kw OR (Nutriceutical):ti,ab,kw OR (Neutraceuticals):ti,ab,kw 922

#10 (Neutraceutical):ti,ab,kw OR (Herbal Supplements):ti,ab,kw OR (Herbal Supplement):ti,ab,kw OR (Herbal Supplement):ti,ab,kw OR (Supplements, Herbal):ti,ab,kw 761

#11 #6 or #7 or #8 or #9 or #10 26738

#12 #5 and #11 307

Supplementary Material 3. Comparisons between dietary supplements

-0.72 (-12.34, 10.96)	-6.19 (-17.37, 5.03)	0.02 (-10.89, 11)	2.6 (-11.2, 16.28)	-3.54 (-13.68, 6.59)	-5.78 (-16.02, 4.24)	0.22 (-10.86, 11.18)	-2.55 (-11.9, 6.79)	1.21 (-9.68, 12.19)	-1.07 (-11.09, 8.74)	HGC									
23.71 (10.85, 36.53)*	18.22 (5.79, 30.56)*	24.45 (12.35, 36.54)*	27 (12.16, 41.68)*	20.88 (9.4, 32.25)*	18.65 (7.14, 29.96)*	24.63 (12.41, 36.72)*	21.88 (11.11, 32.55)*	25.63 (13.52, 37.72)*	23.35 (12.07, 34.41)*	24.42 (11.95, 36.82)*	Lanconone								
12.77 (1.72, 23.95)*	7.3 (-3.55, 18.07)	13.53 (3.02, 24.06)*	16.05 (2.68, 29.35)*	9.94 (0.36, 19.53)*	7.73 (-1.98, 17.2)	13.71 (3.2, 24.22)*	10.94 (2.12, 19.81)*	14.71 (4.2, 25.23)*	12.42 (2.97, 21.69)*	13.5 (2.76, 24.25)*	-10.91 (-22.87, 1.03)	LcS							
6.48 (-3.53, 17.45)	0.93 (-8.35, 11.66)	7.14 (-1.8, 17.57)	9.79 (-2.59, 22.93)	3.63 (-4.57, 12.9)	1.39 (-6.79, 10.61)	7.33 (-1.64, 17.79)	4.53 (-2.47, 13.21)	8.33 (-0.55, 18.76)	6.04 (-1.79, 15.21)	7.13 (-2.21, 17.97)	-17.25 (-28.02, -5.29)*	-6.39 (-15.1, 3.89)	MSM						
13.34 (2.98, 23.84)*	7.87 (-2.1, 17.87)	14.09 (4.47, 23.7)*	16.65 (3.91, 29.42)*	10.53 (1.84, 19.2)*	8.31 (-0.5, 16.91)	14.28 (4.61, 23.93)*	11.51 (3.8, 19.3)*	15.29 (5.69, 24.92)*	13 (4.45, 21.36)*	14.09 (4.09, 24.07)*	-10.35 (-21.62, 0.97)	0.58 (-8.86, 10.04)	6.92 (-2.33, 14.89)*	ParActin					
39.77 (13.63, 65.7)*	34.24 (8.4, 60.04)*	40.49 (14.7, 66.11)*	43.06 (15.87, 70.03)*	36.88 (11.45, 62.12)*	34.7 (9.11, 59.9)*	40.69 (14.74, 66.36)*	37.91 (12.73, 62.76)*	41.69 (15.9, 67.26)*	39.37 (13.95, 64.42)*	40.48 (14.59, 66.1)*	16.06 (-10.34, 42.29)	26.99 (1.27, 52.45)*	33.18 (7.64, 58.22)*	26.42 (0.92, 51.63)*	PFP				
-1.94 (-10.4, 6.63)	-7.4 (-15.32, 0.53)	-1.18 (-8.67, 6.3)	1.37 (-9.87, 12.6)	-4.75 (-11, 1.52)	-6.96 (-13.31, -0.83)	-0.98 (-8.55, 6.5)	-3.74 (-8.7, 1.17)	0.01 (-7.49, 7.56)	-2.27 (-8.26, 3.52)	-1.2 (-9.16, 6.78)	-25.63 (-35.13, -16.02)*	-14.7 (-22.02, -7.4)*	-8.31 (-15.18, -2.97)*	-15.27 (-21.33, -9.23)*	-41.66 (-66.07, -16.95)*	Placebo			
3.27 (-7.6, 14.23)	-2.19 (-12.82, 8.3)	4.01 (-6.17, 14.3)	6.57 (-6.64, 19.75)	0.46 (-8.88, 9.72)	-1.76 (-11.31, 7.46)	4.21 (-6.12, 14.47)	1.46 (-7.15, 10.01)	5.21 (-5.07, 15.46)	2.93 (-6.32, 11.95)	4.01 (-6.65, 14.55)	-20.42 (-32.24, -8.65)*	-9.5 (-19.62, 0.66)	-3.08 (-13.2, 5.31)	-10.08 (-19.28, -0.81)*	-36.49 (-61.83, -10.78)	5.21 (-1.83, 12.2)	UC_II		
1.22 (-9.69, 12.21)	-4.25 (-14.79, 6.27)	1.98 (-8.32, 12.16)	4.53 (-8.61, 17.65)	-1.59 (-10.92, 7.66)	-3.82 (-13.29, 5.41)	2.17 (-8.2, 12.42)	-0.59 (-9.16, 7.92)	3.15 (-7.1, 13.43)	0.88 (-8.34, 9.9)	1.96 (-8.71, 12.52)	-22.48 (-34.19, -10.71)*	-11.55 (-21.7, -1.47)*	-5.13 (-15.31, 3.29)	-12.12 (-21.35, -2.94)*	-38.51 (-63.89, -12.78)	3.15 (-3.89, 10.13)	-2.06 (-11.95, 7.84)	VitaminD	

*P < 0.05; MD, mean difference; CrI, credibility interval; ART, Artemisia; BCC, BioCell Collagen; EM, Eggshell Membrane; GC, glucosamine sulfate and chondroitin sulfate; GH_CS, glucosamine hydrochloride and chondroitin sulfate; HA, hyaluronic acid; HGC, hyaluronic acid, glucosamine and chondroitin; Lcs, *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota; MSM, Methylsulfonylmethane; PFP, passion fruit peel extract; UC_II, undenatured type II collagen;

Table4. Comparisons between the dietary supplements on WOMAC stiffness

MD 95%CrI																
ART																
0.46 (-0.6, 1.52)	BCC															
0.82 (-0.57, 2.21)	0.36 (-0.9, 1.62)	Creatine														
12.6 (-0.6, 25.79)	12.13 (-1.05, 25.32)	11.77 (-1.43, 24.98)	EM													
0.89 (-0.26, 2.04)	0.43 (-0.55, 1.4)	0.07 (-1.27, 1.4)	-11.7 (-24.88, 1.48)	Garlic												
1.52 (0.53, 2.51)*	1.06 (0.28, 1.84)*	0.7 (-0.5, 1.89)	-11.07 (-24.26, 2.12)	0.63 (-0.27, 1.53)	GH_CS											
-0.27 (-1.86, 1.31)	-0.74 (-2.2, 0.73)	-1.09 (-2.82, 0.64)	-12.86 (-26.11, 0.4)	-1.16 (-2.69, 0.38)	-1.79 (-3.21, -0.38)*	HA										
1.02 (-0.08, 2.13)	0.56 (-0.36, 1.48)	0.2 (-1.1, 1.5)	-11.57 (-24.74, 1.62)	0.13 (-0.89, 1.16)	-0.5 (-1.34, 0.34)	1.3 (-0.2, 2.8)	HGC									
2.66 (1.43, 3.89)*	2.2 (1.13, 3.27)*	1.84 (0.44, 3.24)*	-9.93 (-23.14, 3.25)	1.77 (0.62, 2.92)*	1.14 (0.15, 2.14)*	2.94 (1.34, 4.52)*	1.64 (0.52, 2.75)*	Lanconone								
-0.08 (-0.96, 0.81)	-0.54 (-1.19, 0.11)	-0.9 (-2.02, 0.22)	-12.68 (-25.83, 0.5)	-0.97 (-1.75, -0.18)*	-1.6 (-2.12, -1.08)*	0.2 (-1.15, 1.54)	-1.1 (-1.82, -0.38)*	-2.74 (-3.63, -1.84)*	LcS							
3.68 (1.92, 5.46)*	3.22 (1.55, 4.89)*	2.86 (0.97, 4.76)*	-8.91 (-22.15, 4.34)	2.8 (1.08, 4.51)*	2.16 (0.54, 3.78)*	3.96 (1.92, 5.99)*	2.66 (0.97, 4.35)*	1.02 (-0.75, 2.8)	3.76 (2.21, 5.32)*	MSM						
1.71 (0.76, 2.68)*	1.25 (0.5, 2)*	0.89 (-0.28, 2.07)	-10.89 (-24.05, 2.3)	0.82 (-0.04, 1.69)	0.19 (-0.44, 0.82)	1.99 (0.59, 3.38)*	0.69 (-0.12, 1.49)	-0.95 (-1.91, 0.02)	1.79 (1.33, 2.25)*	-1.97 (-3.57, -0.37)*	ParActin					
2.68 (-2.78, 8.17)	2.22 (-3.22, 7.69)	1.86 (-3.64, 7.39)	-9.91 (-24.17, 4.36)	1.79 (-3.65, 7.27)	1.16 (-4.25, 6.6)	2.95 (-2.62, 8.55)	1.66 (-3.78, 7.11)	0.02 (-5.46, 5.5)	2.76 (-2.64, 8.18)	-1.01 (-6.63, 4.64)	0.97 (-4.45, 6.4)	PFP				
-0.08 (-0.94, 0.79)	-0.54 (-1.16, 0.08)	-0.9 (-2, 0.2)	-12.68 (-25.84, 0.5)	-0.97 (-1.73, -0.21)*	-1.6 (-2.08, -1.12)	0.2 (-1.14, 1.52)	-1.1 (-1.79, -0.41)*	-2.74 (-3.61, -1.87)*	0 (-0.2, 0.2)	-3.76 (-5.31, -2.22)*	-1.79 (-2.2, -1.38)*	-2.76 (-8.18, 2.64)	Placebo			
5.92 (4.93, 6.92)*	5.46 (4.67, 6.25)*	5.1 (3.9, 6.3)*	-6.67 (-19.84, 6.51)	5.03 (4.12, 5.94)*	4.4 (3.71, 5.09)*	6.19 (4.77, 7.62)*	4.9 (4.05, 5.75)*	3.26 (2.26, 4.26)*	6 (5.47, 6.53)*	2.24 (0.61, 3.86)*	4.21 (3.57, 4.86)*	3.24 (-2.21, 8.66)	6 (5.5, 6.49)*	UC_II		

*P < 0.05; MD, mean difference; CrI, credibility interval; ART, Artemisia; BCC, BioCell Collagen; CrI, credibility interval; EM, Eggshell Membrane; GH_CS, glucosamine hydrochloride and chondroitin sulfate; HA, hyaluronic acid; HGC, hyaluronic acid, glucosamine and chondroitin; Lcs, *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota; MSM, Methylsulfonylmethane; PFP, passion fruit peel extract; UC_II, undenatured type II collagen.

Table5. Comparisons between the dietary supplements on Total WOMAC

MD 95%CrI																
ART																
8.72 (-2.26, 19.73)	BCC															
4.03 (-8.37, 16.48)	-4.67 (-14.09, 4.74)	COM														
5.16 (-10.61, 20.93)	-3.55 (-17.16, 9.99)	1.12 (-13.64, 15.92)	EM													
5.08 (-5.51, 15.76)	-3.63 (-10.48, 3.22)	1.06 (-7.96, 10.05)	-0.07 (-13.37, 13.3)	Garlic												
5.42 (-5.69, 16.58)	-3.29 (-10.92, 4.39)	1.39 (-8.23, 10.98)	0.3 (-13.44, 14.01)	0.33 (-6.81, 7.47)	GCM											
0 (-11.33, 11.41)	-8.7 (-16.57, -0.83)	-4.03 (-13.83, 5.73)	-5.13 (-19, 8.74)	-5.07 (-12.45, 2.28)	-5.41 (-13.56, 2.73)	GCS										
3.5 (-6.39, 13.4)	-5.21 (-10.83, 0.41)	-0.55 (-8.61, 7.52)	-1.66 (-14.34, 11.08)	-1.59 (-6.44, 3.29)	-1.93 (-7.85, 3.98)	3.49 (-2.74, 9.72)	HA									
2.86 (-8.14, 13.91)	-5.85 (-13.36, 1.63)	-1.18 (-10.63, 8.29)	-2.29 (-15.93, 11.39)	-2.24 (-9.16, 4.69)	-2.56 (-10.29, 5.11)	2.84 (-5.1, 10.78)	-0.65 (-6.34, 5.07)	HGC								
33.35 (20.06, 46.68)*	24.65 (14.06, 35.21)*	29.32 (17.21, 41.37)*	28.19 (12.69, 43.72)*	28.26 (18.08, 38.42)*	27.94 (17.13, 38.62)*	33.34 (22.4, 44.25)*	29.87 (20.46, 39.23)*	30.49 (19.91, 41.12)*	Lanconone							
16.56 (6.58, 26.58)*	7.86 (2.06, 13.67)*	12.54 (4.33, 20.72)*	11.4 (-1.33, 24.22)	11.48 (6.39, 16.56)*	11.13 (5.04, 17.27)*	16.56 (10.14, 22.98)*	13.07 (9.84, 16.29)*	13.71 (7.81, 19.6)*	-16.8 (-26.25, -7.25)*	LcS						
9.46 (-0.81, 19.77)	0.76 (-5.56, 7.06)	5.43 (-3.15, 13.98)	4.31 (-8.64, 17.36)	4.37 (-1.27, 10.01)	4.06 (-2.55, 10.6)	9.46 (2.6, 16.28)*	5.97 (1.94, 9.97)*	6.61 (0.21, 13)*	-23.9 (-33.67, -14.09)*	-7.1 (-11.39, -2.82)*	Micronutrient					
4.83 (-4.89, 14.6)	-3.88 (-9.29, 1.55)	0.79 (-7.14, 8.72)	-0.34 (-12.91, 12.33)	-0.26 (-4.89, 4.38)	-0.59 (-6.35, 5.14)	4.83 (-1.23, 10.86)	1.33 (-1.08, 3.75)	1.98 (-3.52, 7.48)	-28.53 (-37.76, -19.21)*	-11.73 (-14.57, -8.91)*	-4.63 (-8.36, -0.91)*	MSM				
20.76 (10.16, 31.44)*	12.04 (5.16, 18.97)*	16.71 (7.73, 25.71)*	15.6 (2.29, 28.94)*	15.67 (9.37, 21.97)*	15.34 (8.14, 22.48)*	20.74 (13.33, 28.16)*	17.26 (12.34, 22.19)*	17.9 (10.91, 24.89)*	-12.59 (-22.78, -2.37)*	4.19 (-0.94, 9.34)	11.28 (5.6, 16.97)*	15.93 (11.25, 20.59)*	ParActin			
51.36 (19.18, 83.57)*	42.67 (11.48, 73.77)*	47.33 (15.62, 78.92)*	46.27 (13.06, 79.44)*	46.29 (15.23, 77.31)*	45.94 (14.71, 77.13)*	51.34 (20.07, 82.61)*	47.84 (17.09, 78.64)*	48.5 (17.34, 79.72)*	18 (-13.89, 50.05)	34.79 (4.03, 65.6)*	41.89 (10.98, 72.84)*	46.53 (15.77, 77.32)*	30.63 (-0.4, 61.62)	PFP		
-1.25 (-10.91, 8.47)	-9.95 (-15.18, -4.69)*	-5.28 (-13.09, 2.53)	-6.4 (-18.93, 6.17)	-6.33 (-10.76, -1.89)*	-6.66 (-12.25, -1.1)*	-1.25 (-7.16, 4.65)	-4.74 (-6.76, -2.72)*	-4.09 (-9.44, 1.25)	-34.6 (-43.75, -25.39)*	-17.8 (-20.31, -15.31)*	-10.7 (-14.18, -7.23)*	-6.07 (-7.4, -4.74)*	-21.99 (-26.48, -17.52)*	-52.6 (-83.37, -21.9)*	Placebo	

*P < 0.05; MD, mean difference; CrI, credibility interval; ART, Artemisia; BCC, BioCell Collagen; COM, cis-9-cetylmyristoleate; EM, Eggshell Membrane; GCM, glucosamine, chondroitin sulfate, and methylsulfonylmethane; GCS, glucosamine, chondroitin sulfate, and Saccharumlactis; HA, hyaluronic acid; HGC, hyaluronic acid, glucosamine, and chondroitin; Lcs, *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota; MSM, Methylsulfonylmethane; PFP, passion fruit peel extract.

Supplementary Material 4.

Supplementary Material 4. Assessment of publication bias; (A): Visual analog scale (VAS) (B): WOMAC pain (C): WOMAC function (D): WOMAC stiffness (E): Total WOMAC ; ART, *Artemisia*; BCC, BioCell Collagen; COM, cis-9-cetylmyristoleate; EM, eggshell membrane; GC, glucosamine sulfate and chondroitin sulfate; GCM, glucosamine, chondroitin sulfate, and methylsulfonylmethane; GCS, glucosamine, chondroitin sulfate, and saccharumlactis; GH_CS, glucosamine hydrochloride and chondroitin sulfate; GMCTCO, glucosamine, methylsulfonylmethane, chondroitin sulfate, type II collagen, collagen peptide, and olive extract; HA, hyaluronic acid; HGC, hyaluronic acid, glucosamine, and chondroitin; LCS, *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota; MSM, methylsulfonylmethane; PFP, passion fruit peel extract; UC_II, undenatured type II collagen; WOMAC, Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Arthritis Index.

Supplementary Material 5. Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in GRADE

Dietary supplements for osteoarthritis in VAS scores

Patient or population: patients with osteoarthritis

Settings:

Intervention: VAS scores

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Control	VAS scores				
Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in VAS scores VAS Score Follow-up: 8-96 weeks		The mean dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in vas scores in the intervention groups was 1.28 lower (1.94 to 0.61 lower)		255 (6 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ low ^{1,2}	

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval;

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High quality: Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect.

Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

Low quality: Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

Very low quality: We are very uncertain about the estimate.

¹ Indirect comparisons between several randomized controlled trials, each of which compares an intervention to a placebo, rather than head-to-head comparisons are made in randomized controlled trials.

² The study's very limited number of patients and observed incidents resulted in a broader confidence interval.

Supplementary Material 5. Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in GRADE

Dietary supplements for osteoarthritis in WOMAC pain scores

Patient or population: patients with osteoarthritis

Settings:

Intervention: WOMAC Pain

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Control	WOMAC Pain				
Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC pain scores		The mean dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC pain scores in the intervention groups was		1752 (19 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ low ^{1,2}	
WOMAC Pain		1.95 lower				
Follow-up: 8-96 weeks		(2.58 to 1.32 lower)				

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

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¹ Indirect comparisons between several randomized controlled trials, each of which compares an intervention to a placebo, rather than head-to-head comparisons are made in randomized controlled trials.

² The study's limited number of patients and observed incidents resulted in a broader confidence interval.

Supplementary Material 5. Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in GRADE

Dietary supplements for osteoarthritis in WOMAC function scores

Patient or population: patients with osteoarthritis

Settings:

Intervention: WOMAC Function

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Control	WOMAC Function				
Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC function scores		The mean dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC function scores in the intervention groups was 6.45 lower (8.12 to 4.78 lower)		1753 (19 studies)	⊕⊕⊕⊖ low ^{1,2}	
WOMAC Function						
Follow-up: 8-96 weeks						

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval;

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

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Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

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¹ Indirect comparisons between several randomized controlled trials, each of which compares an intervention to a placebo, rather than head-to-head comparisons are made in randomized controlled trials.

² The study's limited number of patients and observed incidents resulted in a broader confidence interval.

Supplementary Material 5. Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in GRADE

Dietary supplements for osteoarthritis in WOMAC stiffness scores

Patient or population: patients with osteoarthritis

Settings:

Intervention: WOMAC Stiffness

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Control	WOMAC Stiffness				
Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC stiffness scores		The mean dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in WOMAC stiffness scores in the intervention groups was		1155 (15 studies)	⊕⊕⊕⊕ very low ^{1,2,3}	
WOMAC Stiffness		0.56 lower				
Follow-up: 8-96 weeks		(0.71 to 0.41 lower)				

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval;

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

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Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

Low quality: Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

Very low quality: We are very uncertain about the estimate.

¹ Indirect comparisons between several randomized controlled trials, each of which compares an intervention to a placebo, rather than head-to-head comparisons are made in randomized controlled trials.

² The study's limited number of patients and observed incidents resulted in a broader confidence interval.

³ Statistical analysis showed publication bias

Supplementary Material 5. Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in GRADE

Dietary supplements for osteoarthritis in total WOMAC scores

Patient or population: patients with osteoarthritis

Settings:

Intervention: Total WOMAC

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Control	Total WOMAC				
Dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in total WOMAC scores Total WOMAC Follow-up: 8-96 weeks		The mean dietary supplement for osteoarthritis in total womac scores in the intervention groups was 8.2 lower (9.08 to 7.31 lower)		1220 (17 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ low ^{1,2}	

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval;

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

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Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

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¹ Indirect comparisons between several randomized controlled trials, each of which compares an intervention to a placebo, rather than head-to-head comparisons are made in randomized controlled trials.

² The study's limited number of patients and observed incidents resulted in a broader confidence interval.